

Dry hot extractors: crafting manual v1.3

Materials (see figures):

- Metal funnels are recommended, plastic or cardboard possible, \varnothing 15-20 cm, steep slope (at least 20 cm height)
- Rubber/silicone connectors between the funnels and the vials. They should be tightly pushed up on the lower narrow part of the funnel and be compatible with the vials for animal storage (e.g. 15-20 ml tubes for microarthropods). The vial lids can be used as the connectors. Alternatively, vials can stand below the funnel
- Metal/plastic kitchen sieves that fit snugly in the funnel with mesh size >2 mm
- Plastic or metal mesh 1 mm size (to filter out large macrofauna)*
- Funnel holder – some device to keep the funnels upright, e.g., a board with holes
- Heat source on top of each funnel or a group of adjacent funnels (e.g. heating halogen or incandescent lamps or ceramic infrared heat emitter ~ 40 Watts)**
- Two plastic shields $\varnothing \sim 40$ cm to put on the table and work with the soil and litter

Instructions: no manual is available; the pictures and elements are given below

Photo credits: Konstantin Gongalsky, Natalia Kuznetsova, Xin Sun, Saori Fujii; Microarthropod drawings: Svenja Meyer

*To extract large invertebrates, a similar setup can be used, but with a 2 cm sieve and 2 layers of coarser mesh (e.g. curtain netting with ~ 1 cm x 2 mm openings); additional openings can be increased by cutting or removing threads. Note that in Soil BON foodweb main design we use hand sorting for large invertebrates.

**Avoid overheating by a too sharp increase in temperature / lamp being too close to the soil.

Example of commercial solution: <http://burkard.co.uk/product/tullgren-funnels-6-and-12-bank/>